

Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11414172>

Leslie B. Amorganda

Teacher II, Demetrio L. Alviola National High School Bindoy, Negros Oriental, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4553-5572> | leslieborladoamorganda@gmail.com

Dr. Antonieta C. Olores

District Supervisor, Bindoy District 1, Philippines
antonieta.olores001@deped.gov.ph
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1068-360X> | antonieta.olores001@deped.gov.ph

Abstract:

Reading proficiency is the essential skill required for academic success, and teachers must be able to identify the reading proficiency level of their learners so that they can plan for effective strategies that will help enhance their learners' reading skills. This study aimed to determine the reading proficiency of grade 6 learners in oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension. The study was tested on 63 grade 6 learners using a self-made questionnaire that passed stringent tests of validity and reliability. The data were statistically analyzed using the mean and t-test. Overall, the reading proficiency of Grade 6 learners was at a frustration level. When grouped according to sex, distance of home from school, average family monthly income, and size of the family, the reading proficiency of Grade 6 learners in the areas of oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension was frustration level. Further, there was a significant difference in the level of reading proficiency of Grade 6 learners in oral reading when compared with family income and family size. Learners' frustration rating in silent reading, reading comprehension, and listening comprehension stems from poor comprehension and trouble in understanding and drawing conclusions from a given reading material.

These calls for DepEd authorities, reading implementers, and school stakeholders to consider the reading profile of the learners in proposing remedial reading programs and in formulating intervention plans to improve the reading proficiency of the learners.

Keywords: Reading Proficiency, Grade 6, Learners, Bindoy, Negros Oriental.

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Reading is the foundation for all academic learning. Proficiency in reading influences academic performance. Learners who are proficient in reading tend to achieve better grades in their academic subjects. On the other hand, learners without the ability to read abound academic, emotional, and social issues. Children who are behind their peers in reading will develop low self-esteem and feelings of inadequacy (Bernanke, 2022).

In a recent survey conducted by UNICEF in year 2022, the reading proficiency of children is one the major problems in poor and developing countries such as Cambodia, Chad, Congo, Ethiopia, Gambia, Mozambique, and Myanmar, which suffered a similar fate of having only less than 15 percent of children able to read a simple text due to the longest school's closure caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (de Vera, 2022). , In the Philippines, the difficulty of learners in reading and comprehending is a problem that has been solved previously, especially in public elementary schools. Despite the Department of Education's initiative to implement programs and activities to promote and enhance the literacy of the learners to read and comprehend, the number of poor reader learners continues to rise after two years of no face-to-face classes (Manaois, 2021).

Upon the return to face-to-face classes, the researcher observed that poor reading comprehension is one of the reasons for having non-readers and frustrated readers in the school she is in. In fact, after conducting the Phil-IRI diagnostics assessment on 29 pupils enrolled in the researcher's class, 4 were identified as a non-reader; 10 were at frustration level 8 were instructional, and another 7 were independent. With the present data, the researcher is alarmed since it is expected that Grade VI pupils are supposed to be independent readers already. This is why the researcher decided to conduct this study to determine the reading proficiency level of the learners. With the result of the study, the researcher will be able to craft appropriate reading activities that will suit every learner's reading difficulty.

Current State of Knowledge

Reading proficiency is the essential skill required for academic success. Children proficient in reading are more likely to do well in subjects other than languages. Reading is every child's foundation where great learning is involved, proving one's comprehension. Reading teachers play a vital role in assessing their pupils' reading skills and administering intervention programs for learners' reading development (Nicolas, 2021). The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) was created to provide classroom teachers with a tool for measuring and describing reading performance. It is an assessment tool composed of graded passages designed to determine a student's reading level. Phil-IRI can be used to assess students' Oral Reading, Silent Reading Comprehension, and Listening Comprehension levels.

Oral reading is one of several critical components required for successful reading comprehension. Oral reading is reading a connected text quickly, accurately, and with expression. Students who read with automaticity and have appropriate speed, accuracy, and proper expression are more likely to comprehend material because they can focus on the text's meaning (Raspica & Cummings, 2014). Fluent oral reading is essential in the successful journey throughout school. Oral reading fluency is a key skill that is a prerequisite for comprehension, as emphasized by Tindal et al. (2016). According to DiSalle and Rasinski (2017), 90% of comprehension problems are due to a deficiency in oral fluency. Thus, students with poor reading fluency in their early academic life likely have problems in later academic stages. For this reason, building and developing literacy skills in the early learning stage is essential. Nicolas (2021) revealed that the oral reading speed of Grade 6 learners falls under frustration level or learners are classified as slow readers based on the Phil-IRI criteria.

Another reading proficiency skill for the learner needs to be mastered in silent reading. Silent reading is generally conceived as a time in which a class, or in some cases an entire school, reads quietly together from self-selected reading materials, ideally with an 'adult to model the habits, choices, comments, and attitudes good readers develop. Kuzmičová et al. (2017) explain that silent reading was often experienced as a social practice and sometimes purposefully performed as such' and that 'participants reported enjoying reading together with other members of their household, sharing not only the same space and time for reading but also exchanging related comment (Merga, 2018). Reutzel and Juth (2014) concluded that developing silent reading is an important goal to be achieved in elementary literacy instruction. Time spent reading silently has consistently correlated strongly with overall student reading. Elementary teachers allocated a block of classroom time for students to go off on their own and read silently. In addition, silent reading provides opportunities for students to practice a variety of reading skills and promotes reading stamina and proficiency. Cabardo (2018) revealed that the majority of the students belonged to the frustration level of reading proficiency in silent reading. Moreover, Miñoza and Montero (2019) revealed that the learners' comprehension of silent reading is average.

Further, another reading proficiency skill that the learner needs to master is Listening Comprehension. Listening Comprehension is part of the [communication skills](#), such as the development of reading and writing comprehension According to Avendano (2021), listening is the interpretation of spoken language, including recognizing discourses of sounds, understanding the meaning of individual words, or understanding the syntax of sentences that may arise in a dialogue or discourse. Listening Comprehension can generate skills for retention, relationship, and understanding of a message. To be able to get the most important things out and to be able to interpret them in the best possible way in order to develop knowledge. It is also important to emphasize that the relevance of listening comprehension is not only to be able to channel and understand a message in the best way but also to know how listening can improve social skills. Ambubuyog et al. (2023), stressed that active listening is vital in language learning and acquisition, with its effects found on multiple aspects of the learning process. Active listening is an underrated skill, and should be attended to by language teachers who take charge of teaching macro skills in communication. In a study conducted by Sumalinog (2018), the majority of the respondents admitted that their average listening comprehension skills had also caused them inconvenience and delays in understanding the listening texts. In addition, the respondents found out that the material they used was a little difficult for them for it revolved around unfamiliar topics. During the test, the level of difficulty exceeded their current comprehension level.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on Proficiency Theory by Knox (1986), which provides a parsimonious explanation of the teaching-learning transaction for learners in all its variety. It contains generalizations regarding human learning as well as generalizations that are especially important for learners with various characteristics, such as reading ability, age, and experiences (Knox, 1986, p. 382). He defined proficiency as the capability to perform satisfactorily if given the opportunity, with performance referring to some combination of attitude, knowledge, and skill. He talked about the need for teachers and learners to understand discrepancies between current and desired proficiencies. He believed that using needs assessment and evaluation activities in examining proficiencies was necessary: "An understanding of discrepancies between current and desired proficiencies help to explain motives of the learners and enables those who help students learn to do so responsively and effectively" (Knox, 1986, p. 16).

Further, Knox (1986) believed that proficiency-oriented learning has the potential to help learners achieve at the highest possible level. In comparing proficiency ideas with competency-based approaches, he noted, "Whereas competency-based preparatory education emphasizes the achievement of minimal standards of performance in educational tasks, proficiency-oriented continuing education emphasizes the achievement of optimal standards of proficiency related to adult life roles" (Knox, 1986, p. 16).

As a link in the present study, proficiency theory will determine the capability of the learners to perform satisfactorily if given the opportunity. By using the Phil-IRI needs assessment and evaluation activities in examining proficiencies, the teachers will understand the discrepancies between the learners' current and desired reading proficiencies. Hence, the teachers may have the opportunity to adjust of his/her teaching methods to the learners and should not hesitate to make necessary changes in them if required.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the reading proficiency of grade 6 learners. More specifically, it aimed to determine: 1) the level of reading proficiency in oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension; 2) the level of reading proficiency of grade 6 learners when grouped according to sex, distance from home to school, average family monthly income, and size of the family; and 3) the significant difference on the level of reading proficiency grade 6 learners when compared according to sex, distance from home to school, average family monthly income, and size of the family.

Methodology

This portion presents the research design, respondents, instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

Research Design

This paper used a descriptive research design to determine the level of reading proficiency of grade 6 learners. Calmorin (2012) cited that this method seeks the real facts in relation to a current situation. Furthermore, this also involves describing, comparing, contrasting and interpreting conditions that exists.

Study Respondents

The total respondents who took the reading proficiency test were 79 grade 6 learners in one of the schools of Negros Oriental. The researcher used purposive sampling, as all respondents to the survey fit a particular profile for the study.

Instrument

This study employed a self-made questionnaire of the reading proficiency in oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension. For oral reading, it is composed of two selections wherein the learners are asked to read aloud. A total of 170 words in the two selections. The teacher listened attentively and identified how many miscues words the learner has after reading the selections. For silent reading, it is also composed of two selections wherein the learners are asked to read silently and answer the 16 items multiple choice questions. Moreover, for listening comprehension, the learners listen to 2 selections as the teacher read aloud, then after the teacher will ask the 16 items multiple choice questions.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. Upon approval, the researcher went to the identified school and presented the approved letter to the school principal. Scheduled appointments were arranged for the actual survey. A consent form was given to the parents to allow their children to be the subject of the study. The questionnaires were administered during the free time of the learners so as to maintain the schedule of classes. The researcher personally administered the test questionnaire to the learners with the assistance of classroom advisers. For oral reading the researcher administered it individually to learners. For silent reading and listening comprehension the researcher allotted 45 minutes for the learners to answer the questions after they silently read and listened the story/selections. After the administration of the test, the researcher recorded the scores of the learners and presented them in tabular form for easy interpretation and analysis of the results. In the presentation of the data, the researcher followed the table of specifications prepared to provide accurate interpretation and analysis of the results.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and weighted mean to determine the level of reading proficiency of grade 6 learners in oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension. Objective No. 2 also used the descriptive analytical scheme and weighted mean to determine the reading proficiency of grade 6 learners when grouped according to sex, distance from to school, average family monthly income, and size of the family. Objective No. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and t-test to determine the significant difference in the level of reading proficiency of grade 6 learners when grouped and compared according to profile variables.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure no human rights are violated during the conduct of research, the researcher gave importance to the respondents' voluntary participation, informed consent, risk of harm, confidentiality, and anonymity. Consent from the parents of the respondents was solicited. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the respondents could withdraw at any time without any consequences. They were informed about the academic purpose of the study. Confidentiality was ensured as only the researcher/s had access to the research data.

Results and Discussions

In this section the data gathered were further treated, presented, analyzed, and interpreted so as to focus on the specific objectives of the study.

Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners in Oral Reading, Silent Reading, and Listening Comprehension

The first objective was to determine the reading proficiency of grade 6 learners in oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension.

Table 1
Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners in Oral Reading, Silent Reading, and Listening Comprehension

Areas	Mean	Interpretation
Oral Reading	71.59	Frustration
Silent Reading	36.07	Frustration
Listening Comprehension	39.66	Frustration

Table 1 reveals the result on the level of reading proficiency of grade 6 learners in the areas of oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension after the administration of tests.

In the area of oral reading, the learners obtained an overall mean of 71.59 interpreted as frustration level. This shows that most of the learners did not pass the oral reading test. The learners find the reading materials/tests so difficult that they cannot successfully respond, recognize, and read with fluency the given texts or words. The text for them was very challenging to read. They were able to read with 71.59% precision only and many of them stopped reading a few times out of confusion on how to correctly read words. Some also experience occasional breaks because of difficulties with some specific unfamiliar words. It suggests that reading teachers continue providing them with reading materials suitable for their needs and grade level and then move to more complex reading texts and those that actually cater to their areas of interest. These can provide avenues for the learners to grow from being frustrated readers to becoming independent ones. The finding relates to that of DiSalle and Rasinski (2017), wherein they found that 90% of comprehension problems are due to a deficiency in oral fluency. Thus, students with poor reading fluency in their early academic life likely have problems in later academic stages. For this reason, building and developing literacy skills in the early learning stage is essential.

In the area of silent reading, the learners obtained an overall mean of 36.07 interpreted as frustration level. This shows that the majority of the learners belonged to the frustration level in terms of their silent reading proficiency with 36.07% precision only. This suggests that the learners find it difficult to read silently the reading materials and cannot successfully respond to the question asked to them after the passage/selection has been read. It is also noted that learners' scores in silent reading are more dispersed as compared to their scores in oral reading. Teachers spend quite a bit of time teaching various reading strategies to the learners in hopes that they will use the techniques during independent silent reading activities. The finding relates to that of Reutzell and Juth (2014), who concluded that developing silent reading is an important goal to be achieved in elementary literacy instruction. Time spent reading silently has consistently correlated strongly with overall student reading. Elementary teachers allocated a block of classroom time for students to go off on their own and read silently. In

addition, silent reading provides opportunities for students to practice a variety of reading skills and promotes reading stamina and proficiency.

In the area of listening comprehension, the learners obtained an overall mean score of 39.66 interpreted as frustration. This indicates that the learners' listening comprehension abilities are poor. After hearing the passage or selection that the teacher had read out, the learners had a precision of 39.66% to correctly respond to the question. This suggests that teachers should allow students the chance to practice listening to native speech before anything else so they can improve their listening skills and avoid disappointment. Guiding learners in the process of listening provides them with the knowledge by which they can successfully complete a listening activity and puts them in control of their learning. The finding relates to that of Ambubuyog et al. (2023), who stressed that active listening is vital in language learning and acquisition, with its effects found on multiple aspects of the learning process. Active listening is an underrated skill, and should be attended to by language teachers who take charge of teaching macro skills in communication.

Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners When Grouped According to Sex, Distance from Home to School, Average Family Monthly Income, and Size of the Family¹

The second objective was to determine the reading proficiency of grade 6 learners when grouped according to according to selected variables.

Table 2
Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners in Oral Reading, Silent Reading and Listening Comprehension When Grouped According to Sex

Areas	Male Mean	Interpretation	Female Mean	Interpretation
Oral Reading	69.07	Frustration	74.77	Frustration
Silent Reading	37.92	Frustration	33.75	Frustration
Listening Comprehension	39.25	Frustration	40.18	Frustration

Table 2 reveals the results on the level of reading proficiency of Grade 6 learners in the areas of oral reading, silent reading and listening comprehension when grouped according to sex. Both males and females obtained a frustration level on oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension. Analyzing the mean results closely, in the area of oral reading, it is evident a great difference in the mean results; the male group got 69.07 or frustration level while the female group was 74.77 or frustration level. In the area of silent reading, the male group got 37.92 or frustration level while the female group was 33.75 only interpreted as frustration level. In the area of listening comprehension, the male group obtained a mean score of 39.25 or frustration level while for female group was 40.18 or frustration level.

The results suggest that female learners have better oral reading and listening comprehension proficiency than of male learners. However, male learners performed better than female learners on silent reading proficiency. Gender has a unique influence on reading proficiency. Therefore, gender should be kept as a constant factor in any training on reading proficiency. Teachers need to promote activities that will encourage males and females to improve their attitudes toward reading without distractions, whatsoever.

The result aligns with that of Agabon (2021) revealed female learners obtained higher ratings on reading comprehension skills than males. However, in the study of Lagarto (2021), male learners are slightly ahead in oral reading proficiency in English and Filipino. Meanwhile, in the study of Miñoza and Montero (2019), female learners outperformed males in silent reading proficiency. Further, Owolewa (2017) revealed that female students had better performance in listening comprehension compared to their male counterparts.

Table 3
Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners in Oral Reading, Silent Reading and Listening Comprehension When Grouped According to Distance from Home to School

Areas	Nearer Mean	Interpretation	Farther Mean	Interpretation
Oral Reading	69.51	Frustration	73.63	Frustration
Silent Reading	32.26	Frustration	36.87	Frustration

Listening Comprehension	39.31	Frustration	40.00	Frustration
-------------------------	-------	-------------	-------	-------------

Table 3 discloses the results on the level of reading proficiency of Grade 6 learners in the areas of oral reading, silent reading and listening comprehension when grouped according to distance from home to school. Both groups of learners who lived near and far from home to school obtained a frustration level on oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension. Examining the mean results comprehensively, in the area of oral reading, it is noticeable a big difference in the mean results; learners who lived nearer to school got 69.51 or frustration level while those learners who live farther from home to school got 73.63 or frustration level. In the area of silent reading, learners who lived nearer to school obtained a mean score of 32.26, or frustration level while those learners who lived farther from school was 36.87 interpreted as frustration level. In the area of listening comprehension, learners who lived nearer to school obtained a mean score of 39.31 or frustration level while for learners who lived farther from school was 40.00 or frustration level.

The result implies that learners who lived farther from school have higher reading proficiency than learners who lived nearer to school, particularly in oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension. This is because learners who lived farther from school spend their time wisely while at school and spend their free time reading books because they have to spend longer hours traveling to school. Long walking distance is a common phenomenon that learners endure, and it poses psychological and physical repercussions and health hazards. The learners suffer from fatigue and poor concentration in class after spending long hours on the road to get there, and home again.

The finding relates to that of Taiwo (2019) revealed that walking long distances to and from school on a daily basis has a negative impact on students' performance as it could promote absenteeism and fatigue leading to a lack of concentration and interest in reading and school activities. Thomas (2016) revealed that learners traveling substantial distances to school would be exposed to longer time spent in transit, which may detract from the time they can spend on homework or preparing for the next day of school. Nelson, Misra, Sype, and Mackie (2016) reported that students who live farther away from a school find it difficult to complete outside-school tasks requested by their teachers.

Table 4
Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners in Oral Reading, Silent Reading and Listening Comprehension When Grouped According to Average Family Monthly Income

Areas	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
Oral Reading	77.37	Frustration	65.37	Frustration
Silent Reading	35.66	Frustration	36.51	Frustration
Listening Comprehension	40.39	Frustration	38.87	Frustration

Table 4 divulges the results on the level of reading proficiency of Grade 6 learners in the areas of oral reading, silent reading and listening comprehension when grouped according to average family monthly income. Both groups of learners with lower and higher average family monthly income obtained a frustration level on oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension. However, evaluating the mean results carefully, in the area of oral reading, can be seen a great difference in the mean results; learners who belonged to lower-income families got a mean score of 77.37 or frustration level while those learners who belonged to a higher-income family got 65.37 only or frustration level. In the area of silent reading, learners who belonged to lower-income families obtained a mean score of 35.66 or frustration level while those learners who belonged to the higher-income family got a mean score of 36.51 or frustration level. In the area of listening comprehension, learners who belonged to a lower income family obtained a mean score of 40.39 or frustration level while for learners who came from a higher income family was 38.87 or frustration level.

The above facts, it implies that learners who belonged to a lower-income family showed higher ratings in oral reading and listening comprehension compared to learners from higher-income families. However, on silent reading, learners from a higher-income family outperformed learners from a lower-income family. It shows that learners from lower-income families have an advantage over their counterparts group on oral reading and listening comprehension. On the contrary, they were left behind by learners from a lower income family on silent reading proficiency. It further implies that the economic status of the family affects greatly gaining proficiency skills of their children. Many learners are living with the disadvantages that come with low economic status that are far outside of their control and ultimately make learning a more challenging task. Disadvantages set learners behind and cause learners to read below their intended expectancies.

The finding aligns with that of Tuell (2021) revealed that there are notable disadvantages tied to students living in a low socioeconomic background such as little if any support at home as well as a lack of resources made available. Likewise, Villados (2020) revealed that the level reading abilities of learners from a higher income family performed greatly than their counterparts.

Table 5
Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners in Oral Reading, Silent Reading and Listening Comprehension When Grouped According to Size of the Family

Areas	Smaller Mean	Interpretation	Bigger Mean	Interpretation
Oral Reading	58.00	Frustration	77.53	Frustration
Silent Reading	32.81	Frustration	37.50	Frustration
Listening Comprehension	36.02	Frustration	41.25	Frustration

Table 5 exposes the result on the level of reading proficiency of Grade 6 learners in the areas of oral reading, silent reading and listening comprehension when grouped according to the size of the family. Both groups of learners who came from a smaller and bigger family obtained a frustration level on oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension. However, verifying the mean results correctly, in the area of oral reading, it is a very clear great difference in the mean results; learners from a smaller family got 58.00 or frustration level while those learners from a bigger family got 77.53 or frustration level. In the area of silent reading, learners who came from smaller families obtained a mean score of 32.81, or frustration level while those learners from a bigger family were 37.49 interpreted as frustration level. In the area of listening comprehension, learners who came from smaller families obtained a mean score of 36.02 or frustration level while for learners who came from a bigger family was 41.25 or frustration level.

The result implies that the majority of the learner who came from a bigger family have better reading proficiency than learners from a smaller size family particularly on oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension. However, parental attention by parents declines as the number of children increases in the family, hence, some learners from a bigger size family learn to read independently for them not to be left behind by peers. Some learners asked for assistance from their older siblings' reading activities.

The result relates to that of Adongo et al (2022), who revealed that family size characteristics have an influence on students' academic achievement. A small family influences academic achievement more than a large family. However, in the study conducted by Chung et al (2019), adolescent learners that get together with siblings and dialogue with family members obtained the best results in reading comprehension. In addition, Oliveira et al (2016), learners with strong connections with their family members tend to present the best results in reading comprehension.

Comparative Analysis Between the Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

The third objective was to determine the significant difference between the reading proficiency of grade 6 learners when grouped and compared according to variables.

Table 6
Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners in Oral Reading When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	P-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	44	69.07	-1.157	0.251		Not Significant
	Female	35	74.77				
Distance From Home to School	Nearer	39	69.51	-0.836	0.406	0.05	Not Significant
	Farther	40	73.63				

Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	41	77.37	2.525	0.014	Significant
	Higher	38	65.37			
Size of the Family	Smaller	24	58.00	-3.995	0.000	Significant
	Bigger	55	77.53			

Table 6 shows the comparative analysis of the reading proficiency of grade 6 learners in oral reading when compared according to variables. The computed p-values for variable sex and distance from to school are 0.251 and 0.406 indicating no significant difference. However, for variables average family monthly income and size of the family the computed p-values are 0.014 and 0.000 indicating a significant difference. The result implies that the level of reading proficiency of grade 6 learners in the area of oral reading varies when they are compared according to average family monthly income and size of the family, while do not vary when compared according to sex and distance of home from school. This means that those learners belong to different family economic statuses and the number of individuals in the family do significantly differ in their proficiency level when performing oral reading activities. This further suggests that the average family income and size of the family are factors influencing the learner's oral reading proficiency. Average family income and size of the family are considered significant predictors of the oral reading ability of the learners. This is because the basic needs of certain learners are not being met, thus, not allowing the learners to physically and mentally be able to perform reading activities in school.

The result aligns with that of Li et al (2021) revealed that family economic status had both direct and indirect effects on reading development. Likewise, Chung et al. (2017), revealed that children from low-income families had significantly lower levels of reading achievement and language abilities before and after entering formal schooling than those from higher-income families. On the other hand, Olagundoye and Adebile (2019) concluded that large family size no doubt has a negative influence on students' performance in English. Ella et al (2015) also revealed a significant influence of family size and family type on the academic achievement of students. Further, Amagan (2018) revealed that the size of the family has a significant effect on the reading comprehension skills of grade 3 learners.

Table 7
Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners in Silent Reading When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	P-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	44	37.92	1.565	0.122		Not Significant
	Female	35	33.75				
Distance From Home to School	Nearer	39	35.26	-0.601	0.550		Not Significant
	Farther	40	36.87				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	41	35.66	-0.315	0.753	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	38	36.51				
Size of the Family	Smaller	24	32.81	-1.629	0.107		Not Significant
	Bigger	55	77.53				

Table 7 summarizes the comparative analysis of the reading proficiency of grade 6 learners in silent reading when compared according to variables. The computed p values are 0.122, 0.550, 0.753, and 0.107, respectively, indicating no significant differences. The result implies that the level of reading proficiency of Grade 6 learners in the area of silent reading when compared according to sex, distance of home from school, average family monthly income, and size of the family do differs. This suggests that the profile background of the learners was not an intervening factor that differs the silent reading proficiency of the learners. This is because most of the learners have the same level of silent reading proficiency regardless of background.

The result aligns with that of Agabon (2021) revealed that there is no significant difference in the level of comprehension skills of grade 5 learners when compared according to their profile variables. However, in the study Cañete (2017) revealed that the level of reading readiness of grade one learners differs significantly when they are compared according to sex, average family monthly income, parents' educational attainment, and size of the family.

Table 8

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 6 Learners in Listening Comprehension When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	P-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	44	39.25	-0.257	0.798	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	35	40.18				
Distance From Home to School	Nearer	39	39.31	-0.191	0.849	0.05	Not Significant
	Farther	40	40.00				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	41	40.40	0.426	0.671	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	38	38.87				
Size of the Family	Smaller	24	36.02	-1.358	0.179	0.05	Not Significant
	Bigger	55	41.25				

Table 8 shows the comparative analysis of the reading proficiency of grade 6 learners in listening comprehension when compared according to variables. The computed p-values are 0.798, 0.849, 0.671, and 0.179, respectively, indicating no significant differences. The result implies that the level of reading proficiency of Grade 6 learners in the area of listening comprehension do not vary when compared according to sex, distance of home from school, average family monthly income, and size of the family. This suggests that regardless of learners' profile background they performed the same level of reading proficiency on listening comprehension.

The finding relates to that of Cabalo (2019) revealed that sex, age, and family income do not affect the reading ability of the pupils because they are from far-flung barangays and that this profile does not have any intervention as reflected in the PHIL-IRI test results.

Conclusion

Overall, learners' frustration rating in silent reading, reading comprehension, and listening comprehension stems from poor comprehension and trouble in understanding and drawing conclusions from a given reading material. Learners reading proficiency is expected to slow down due to the learners' lack of exposure to various reading drills and activities. The participants need to be exposed to different teaching methods and strategies for reading to uplift their performance in reading and enhance their confidence to read independently. Conducting a daily 15-minute oral reading, silent reading activity and a 20-minute technology assisted learning comprehension would help increase learners' reading proficiency level. These calls for DepEd authorities, reading implementers, and school stakeholders to consider the reading profile of the learners in proposing remedial reading programs and in formulating intervention plans to improve the reading proficiency of the learners.

The researcher would like to express her gratitude and appreciation to the following individuals who helped in the completion of this endeavor. Dr. Antonieta C. Olores, Dr. Lilybeth P. Eslabon, Dr. Randof L. Asistido, Dr. Rey Eslabon, and Dr. Grace M. Abao. To her beau Konstantin Skodras and her family and most of all, to the Divine Providence, whose power and blessings made everything for the realization of his work.

References

- Adongo, A. & Dapaah, J. & Wireko, D. (2022). The influence of family size on academic performance of high school students in Ghana. *SN Social Sciences*. 2. 10.1007/s43545-022-00478-6.
- Agabon, P. (2020). *Comprehension skills of grade 5 pupils: basis for a reading intervention plan*. [Unpublished Master's Thesis]. STI West Negros University.
- Amagam, MJ. (2018). *Reading comprehension skills in relation to mathematics performance*. [Unpublished Masters Thesis]. STI West Negros University.
- Ambubuyog, E & Laumoc, G. & Mantac, F. & Pagulayan, F. & Sayson, C., Velasco, A. & Biray, B. (2023). Active listening: its impact on language learning and understanding of eEducation students. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*. 4(1), 671-676. 10.11594/ijmaber.04.02.33.
- Avendaño, Y. (2021, March 8.). *Influence of Isabel Solé's reading strategies on the reading comprehension of fifth grade primary school educators*. Research Artucilo, 9. doi: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3133-7912>

- Bernanke, B. (2022, September 5). *What's the impact of poor reading?* The children reading foundation. <https://www.readingfoundation.org/the-impact>
- Cabalo, J. (2019). Factors affecting pupils' reading proficiency in multi-grade classes among rural elementary schools. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies*, 02(02), 108-124.
- Cabardo, J. R. (2018). Reading proficiency level of students: basis for reading intervention program. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. 10.2139/ssrn.2712237.
- Calmorin, L. P. (2012). *Research Method and Thesis Writing* (2nd ed.) Rex Bookstore, Inc.
- Cañete, A. (2017). *A comparative analysis of grade one pupils' reading readiness: basis for reading intervention plan*. [Unpublished master's thesis]. STI West Negros University.
- Chavez, J. D., & Maguate, G. S. (2023). ANALYSIS OF PUPILS' MISCONCEPTIONS IN SOLVING NON ROUTINE WORD PROBLEMS. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education (IJARIE)*, 9(04), 1938-1944.
- Chung, G. & Phillips, J. & Jensen, T. M. & Lanier, P. (2019). Parental involvement and adolescents' academic achievement: latent profiles of mother and father warmth as a moderating influence. *Family Process*, x, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/famp.12450>
- De Vera, B. (2022, April 4). *Lockdown's impact: Unicef cites poor reading skills among PH kids*. Philippine Inquirer. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1576573/lockdowns-impact-unicef-cites-poor-reading-skills-among-ph-kids>
- DiSalle, K. & Rasinski, T. (2017) Impact of short-term intense fluency instructions on students' reading achievement: a classroom-based, teacher-initiated research study. *Journal of Teacher Action Research* 3(1), 1-13.
- Ella, E. & Odok, A. (2015). Influence of family size and family type on students' academic performance in Government in Calabar Municipality of Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal for Humanities, Social Sciences and Education*. 2(11), 108-114.
- Kiew, S. & Shah, P. (2020) Factors affecting reading comprehension among Malaysian ESL elementary learners. *Creative Education*, 11(1), 2639-2659.
- Knox, A.B. (1986). Proficiency theory of adult learning. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 5, 378-404.
- Kuzmicova, A. & Mangen, A. & Støle, H., & Begnum, A. C. (2017). Literature and readers' empathy: a qualitative text manipulation study. *Language and Literature*. 26(1), 137-152.
- Lagarto, R. (2020). Reading proficiency level among grade 7: basis for reading intervention program. *International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science*, 6(1), 233-236.
- Li, M. & Koh, P. W. & Geva, E. & Joshi, R M & Chen, X. (2020). The componential model of reading in bilingual learners. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. 112. 10.1037/edu0000459.
- Manaois, D. (2021) Factors affecting the reading comprehension and performance of grade 6 pupils. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(3), 159-171.
- Maguate, G. S., & Rabacal, J. S. (2023). Peer Mentoring for Academic Performance of Students in Science. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 6(06), 183-189.
- Merga, M. K. (2018). Reading aloud: children's attitudes toward being read to at home and at school. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*: 43(3), 123-139.
- Miñoza, M., & Montero, M. (2019). Reading comprehension level among intermediate learners. *ERIC - Education Resources Information Center*. 31(3), 561-568.
- Nelson, D. & Misra, K. & Sype, G. E. & Mackie, W. (2016). An analysis of the relationship between distance from campus and GPA of commuter students. *Journal of International Education Research*, 12(1), 37-46.
- Nicolas, V. (2021). Utilization of online oral reading test in determining the reading skills of the grade 6 pupils in English. *Journal of World English and Educational Practices (JWEEP)*. 3(4), 1-7.
- Olagundoye, C., & Adebile, R.F. (2019). Family size influence of students' attitude and performance in literature-in- English in public secondary schools. *Asian Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*. 1(1), 121-127.
- Oliveira, A. G. & Conceição, M. C. P. & Figueiredo, M. R. & Campos, J. L. M. & Santos, J. N. & Martins-Reis, V. O. (2016). Association between the performance in reading of words and the availability of home environment resources. *Audiology - Communication Research*, 26, 1-10

- Owolewa, O. (2017). Influence of attitude and gender on listening comprehension of senior secondary school students in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Developing Country Studies*, 7(7), 51-56.
- Philippine Informal Reading Inventory Manual (Phil-IRI) (2018). Department of Education -Bureau of Learning Resources (DepEd-LR)
- Raspica, C. & Cummings, K. (2013). Oral reading fluency. *Council for Learning Disabilities*. 51(2), 124-136.
- Reutzell, D. R. & Juth, S. (2014). Supporting the development of silent reading fluency: an evidence-based framework for the intermediate grades (3-6). *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 7(1), 27-46.
- Salutin, M. A., & Maguate, G. (2023). Values-Based Exercises for the Development of Reading Readiness Skills for Preschool Children. *International Journal of scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 11(08), 22-30.
- Sumalinog, G. (2018). Factors affecting the listening comprehension skills of the foreign students. *International Review of Social Sciences*, 6(11), 611-617.
- Taiwo, O. R. (2019). Impact of school plants planning on primary school pupils' academic performance. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 5(9), 83-90.
- Thomas, C. A. (2016). *Going the distance!: How distance to school relates to student education outcomes*. [Published Doctoral Dissertation], University of California.
- Tindal, G. & Nese, J. F. T. & Stevens, J. J., & Alonzo, J. (2016). Growth on oral reading fluency measures as a function of special education and measurement sufficiency. *Remedial and Special Education*, 37(1), 28-40.
- Tuell, L. (2021). *Socioeconomic impact on reading comprehension*. [Published Thesis], California State University.
- Villados, S.R. (2020). *Reading abilities of grade 3 learners in relations to their academic performance: basis for an intervention plan*. [Unpublished Master's Thesis]. STI West Negros University.

Bio-Note

Leslie B. Amorganda is a Teacher II at Demetrio L. Alviola National High School - Senior High School. She holds a bachelor's degree in Secondary Education major in English. She is currently pursuing the Master of Arts in Education major in Administration and Supervision at the STI West Negros University School of Graduate Studies.